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Synergistic effect of dual-scale carbon fillers on sensitivity and stability of flexible strain sensors

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Background

- **Motivation:** stretchable strain /pressure sensor
- Health monitoring (aged care)
- Cancer rehabilitation and wound healing
- Sports performance monitoring
- Soft robotics

Background

Sensing mechanisms: stretchable strain / pressure sensors (strain/stress, motion)

- **Piezoresistive (easy to fabricate)**
- Capacitive
- Piezoelectric

Piezoresistive

Capacitive

Piezoelectric

Background

Conventional strain gauges made of metal foil and semiconductors

- limited to stretchability less than 5%
- Low gauge factor ~ 2

$$\text{Gauge factor (GF)} = \left(\frac{\Delta R / R_0}{\varepsilon} \right)$$

ΔR – the change in resistance caused by strain

R – the resistance of undeformed gauge

ε – strain

Stretchable strain sensors based on conductive nanocomposites

- High stretchability ($\varepsilon \geq 50\%$)
- Tuneable gauge factor
- Low cost

Background

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Current Challenge:

Design wearable strain sensors combining high sensitivity with high stretchability.

Design wearable strain sensors with high stability (**low drift**).

Research Objectives

Aims:

- Design wearable strain sensors with high sensitivity and high stretchability by introducing **dual-scale carbon fillers into PDMS nanocomposites**;
- **Optimize the sensing performance** by adjusting the carbon fillers content.

Advantages:

- Avoiding **high loading of conductive nanofillers**.
- **Easily to scale up**

Fabrication and SEM morphology

1D carbon filler: Carbon nanofibers (CNFs)

2D carbon filler: Graphene Nanoplates (GNPs)

Sandwich structure

Linearity

- Sensors' range of linearity is determined as the strain at which the gauge factor seen as below, would deviate by 10% from its initial value

$$k_i = (R/R_0)_i / \varepsilon_i$$

- This new type of **dual-scale** carbon filler sensors display a **great linear range up to a large strain ($\sim 50\%$)**.

Sensitivity

- The gauge factor is increasing with the dual-scale filler concentration.
- GNP filler play a key role in improving the gauge factor.
- Strain sensor for 15 mg/ml CNF+3GNP (CNF:GNP=1:3) exhibits a gauge factor value of ~ 5.1 (Linear display data: ~ 20.4) and a linearity up to a strain of 47.0% .

Stability (quantitatively analyse drift)

$$f(N) = \frac{k_N}{k_1} = a + (1 - a)e^{-b(N-1)}$$

where k_1 denotes the gauge factor at the first cycle of a given loading block.

The fitting parameter b in the above-mentioned formula indicates the rate of drift of the strain sensors under repeated stretching

By comparison, the hybrid CNFs and GNPs strain sensors (15 mg/ml CNFs+5GNPs, 15 mg/ml CNFs+3GNPs, 15 mg/ml CNFs+GNPs) exhibit a largely improved stability with smaller k_N/k_1 value.

Synergistic Effect

$$\text{Synergy ratio} = \left(\frac{A_{CNFs+GNPs}}{\gamma * A_{CNFs} + (1 - \gamma) * A_{GNPs}} - 1 \right) \times 100\%$$

A could be gauge factor k , linearity LR , stability b , modulus E and stretchability ϵ_f .

Types of strain sensor	Linearity	Gauge factor
15 mg/ml CNFs/PDMS	6.2%	2.20
15 mg/ml GNPs/PDMS	24.3%	7.04
15 mg/ml CNFs+3GNPs/PDMS	47.0%	5.13
Types of strain sensor	Predicted linearity	Predicted gauge factor
15 mg/ml CNFs+3GNPs/PDMS	19.4%	5.69

The hybrid sensors demonstrated the **significant synergistic effects** in both increasing the **linearity range (LR)** and **reducing cyclic drift (fitting parameter b)**, achieving substantially enhanced linearity range and significantly lower drift rate when compared with equivalent sensors containing only CNFs or GNPs.

Piezoresistivity Mechanism

The schematic diagrams illustrate **the dominant mechanism of microcracking** of the strain sensors under small and large strain. The introduction of **CNF fillers bridged the gap between GNPs** to enhance the conductive network.

Application

- Detect different human joint movements
- Good reproducibility and sensitivity

Thanks for your attention!